

Social disinvestment and vulnerable groups in Europe in the aftermath of the financial crisis

The case of young people in Portugal

Graça Costa

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Executive summary

This report is prepared in the framework of the Europe H2020 project ‘Rebuilding an inclusive, value based Europe of solidarity and trust through social investments’ (RE-InVEST). The project aims to evaluate the social investment strategy of the European Commission implemented in 2013 in response to the social damage of the financial crisis in 2008. The RE-InVEST consortium aims to assess the social damage of the crisis drawing from human rights and capability based approaches and focuses on those vulnerable groups mostly affected by the crisis in the 12 countries (and 13 regions) (UK (=EN+SC), IE, PT, NL, RO, LV, IT, BE, DE, AT, CH) covered by the study. The analyses are carried out by the local partners, who consist of NGOs and/or research institutions.

Portugal has been particularly hard hit by the economic crisis. The high unemployment, low employment, rising of poverty and social exclusion, and declining household incomes resulted in a lack of confidence concerning to occupation safety and future economic growth. Social expenditure played a strong role in stabilising household incomes; nonetheless it was reduced due to the sovereign debt crisis. As new entrants to labour market, young people face serious difficulties to get a job. This is mostly exacerbated when they do not receive any kind of social protection and moreover are obliged to accept job offers.

The focus of the research on young unemployed is due to the fact of the unemployment being the major problem among young people under 25 years old. This group has been so severely hit by the economic crisis and so it is a great concern and a top priority¹ among EU Member States. As other countries, Portugal needs to reduce youth unemployment. According to the Monthly Employment and Unemployment Estimates (Instituto Nacional de Estatística – INE (National Statistical Institute) March 2015, the unemployment rate among young people stood at 35.0%² (unemployment of 25-64 year-olds in Portugal is 14.5% compared to the OECD average of 7.5%).

This report examines how young unemployed (18 to 30 years) well-being has been affected by the economic crisis in Portugal. Their difficulties and social constraints in getting a decent job undermine their trust in planning their future and make a smooth transition to adulthood. Young people in precarious employment face higher job insecurity and uncertainty about the future³, which are relevant negative factors affecting the possibility to plan their life and to establish their goals according to reasonable expectations about upcoming opportunities.

The RE-InVEST consortium has jointly developed the PAHRCA – a methodology that combines principles of Participatory Action research with Human Rights and Capability Approaches. This qualitative, participatory research does not produce representative results but rather aims to deepen the understanding of economic, social, cultural and political impacts of the crisis on the lives of vulnerable people and give them a voice.

The biographies of B. and Z. draw a picture of how the crisis has been affecting individual’s life stories. B illustrated her resilience to cope with her father’s emigration to Angola and the effort to not give up her studies during the economic crisis, taking care of her brothers and trying to find a decent job and not emigrating herself after finishing her nursing degree:

1 In the 2015 Annual Growth Survey, the Commission called for determined action to improve the labour market situation of young people, with the Youth Guarantee representing an ambitious way to combine different instruments to address youth unemployment effectively. Thematic fiche youth unemployment European semester (European Commission, 2015).

2 http://observatorio-lisboa.eapn.pt/ficheiro/Destaque-INE_Emprego-e-Desemprego-Março2015.pdf
<http://www.eapn.eu/images/stories/docs/EAPN-position-papers-and-reports/2014-EAPN-youth-poverty-position-paper.pdf>, p.18.

3 EAPN (2013): p. 20.

'I already had job proposals from Norway and I said no! I already had proposals from Belgium, from Germany, from the UK, thousands of them...But it is difficult...I'm not a person who gives up! ...Here the jobs require young people to have lots of experience. Because of this I feel frustrated...So emigration is becoming more and more a strong option.'

Z tells the story of precarious jobs and training in a household very challenging for those who face unemployment because of the crisis:

from June 2011 to December 2015, I was employed one year and eleven months and was unemployed during two years and five months.

Preface

First of all we would like to express our gratitude to the young unemployed people who actively participated in RE-InVEST expressing their feelings, their opinions and experiences associated with unemployment during the economic crisis and their recommendations to national and European politicians and institutions. Without their participation it would not have been possible to write this report. We would like also to thank the *Associação Ecos Urbanos* for helping us to identify the young unemployed people. It is a grassroots' social organisation engaged in the fight against poverty and social exclusion particularly affecting young people. Last but not least we would also like to express our appreciation to the European Commission for financing this project.

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Introduction

The ‘Europe 2020’ strategy is based on a vision of smart, sustainable and inclusive growth, through high levels of employment, productivity and social cohesion. Economic growth is a way of improving life standards but needs to be sustainable by reducing social inequalities and ensure that the benefits are fairly distributed across society. It aims to reduce the number of people in or at risk of poverty and social exclusion in the EU by at least 20 million and increase 75% the employment rate during the 10 years. Nonetheless, the EU is getting off-track in relation to the social inclusion target where 1 in 4 people face poverty and social exclusion (122 million) and increasing inequality between and within Member States. Unemployment and poverty increased due to the economic crisis and the social climate worsened by the cuts in social protection mainly in the southern countries. In 2013, the Commission launched a major endeavour to rebalance economic and social progress: the Social Investment Package (SIP). In the framework of Europe 2020, Portugal had aimed to reach 71% of employment rate in the active population between 20 and 64 years old in 2014 and to reach 75% in 2020. This meant a reduction of 50,000 people in 2014 and a reduction of 200,000 by 2020. The 2014 goals were not reached (the employment rate was 50.6%, and the poverty rate 26.7% after social transferences).

RE-InVEST aims to fill this gap by evaluating the SIP from a human rights and capability approach. The first stage is a diagnosis of the social damage of the crisis in terms of (erosion of) human rights, social (dis) investment, loss of (collective) capabilities, and loss of trust. In order to have a broad and representative scope of the social damage of the crisis, 12 countries are involved (13 regions) in collecting testimonies or ‘narratives of risk’ of people most affected by the crisis, illustrating how it has impacted on their basic human/social rights and how some anti-crisis policies, have reinforced these mechanisms. The current national report aims to analyse the impact of the crisis on youth unemployment (people aged 18 to 30 years old) in Portugal assuming the two project research questions:

1. the crisis has negative social consequences which undermined the human rights of vulnerable groups;
2. the negative social consequences leads to a growing distrust and loss of solidarity.

The priority issues linked with the first hypothesis that came out from young unemployed were dimensions such as: education (Section 4.1.1), employment (Section 4.1.2), social protection (Section 4.1.3); health (Section 4.1.4), and housing (Section 4.1.5). In what concerns to (dis)trust young unemployed people emphasised this subject towards neighbours (Section 4.2.1) and family (Section 4.2.2), social organisations (Section 4.2.3), public services like social security (Section 4.2.4) and public employment service (Section 4.2.4), political institutions (Section 4.2.5) their opinion about refugees (4.2.6) and the meaning of Human Rights (4.2.7). The qualitative data was gathered through a participatory research process which stresses the partnership approach and exchange of knowledge among all stakeholders involved in the project. The project reflects the experience of the most vulnerable people and expresses the personal and societal consequences of unemployment. The testimonies of the unemployed youth reflect the impact of the austerity measures on their daily lives from many points of view: how unemployment affects psychological factors (self confidence and self-esteem; depression and lack of motivation; plans for the future to have their own family as well as leaving their parents’ house), and social factors (to be out of labour market and being forced

to take low-paid jobs, to voluntary ‘downgrade’ their skills when looking and applying for a job, and to decrease the investment in the curriculum development).

This report about the social damage of the crisis experienced by young unemployed people in Portugal is structured in five sections. After the introduction, section one explores the national context and gives a picture of the main social indicators and on how austerity measures undermine individual and collective capabilities and social rights of the most vulnerable and worsen their labour market chances, particularly among young unemployed people. The second section is dedicated to the theoretical framework of the Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA) under RE-InVEST in a brief way. The third section provides details of the two testimonies of unemployed youth that show how economic crisis impacted on their lives. Section four presents a detailed analysis of the testimonies based on their memories regarding education, employment, health, social protection, level of trust in politicians, social organisations, and family. Finally the fifth section presents the conclusions on how young people have been struggling with the economic crisis from the human rights perspective, capabilities and trust; and draws out some recommendations in relation to unemployed people and labour market policies.

1. National context

Between May 2011 and June 2014 Portugal was submitted to an economic adjustment programme and European assistance. The Portuguese government prioritised harsh austerity measures which have resulted in a deterioration of the labour market and the social situation in the name of fiscal consolidation.⁴ Austerity measures undermined social investment, with health reducing costs by more than 500 million euro per year and education cuts of 175 million per year.⁵ Between October 2010 and August 2014 almost 592,000 beneficiaries lost their children's social benefits. The share of people who do not receive income support is particularly high, more than 40% of people living in families with no (or almost no) work and the poor receive only up to 10% of their income as social transfers. In addition, the austerity measures undermined the responsiveness of public service provision by cutting in social protection which led to a further increase of poverty and social exclusion which deeply depended on social transferences.

Furthermore, Portugal is the 9th most unequal country among the OECD countries.⁶ The risk of poverty increased from 17.9% in 2008 to 19.5% in 2013, the highest since 2004 (27.4% of the total Portuguese population) and the poverty rate among the unemployed has reached around 40% in 2013, which amounts to double the total of the general population. The number of working poor increased around 10%. The increase of inequality in labour income was strongly influenced by the effects of unemployment. The impact of the austerity measures in fundamental rights during 2013 and 2014 was maintained or strengthened: reduction of 2% in the number of public sector workers; dismissal of workers with fixed-term contracts, reduction of compensation for overtime; increase in working hours of public employees from 35 to 40 hours a week, without additional compensation; increase of the minimum age for retirement (the normal age of entitlement to an old-age pension in 2014 and in 2015, being now 66 years); increase of the workers' contribution to the special public employees 'health insurance schemes', to 3.5%; new increase of the maximum VAT rate to 23.25% and increase of the workers' contribution to social security to 11.2%. The measures and impact on the right to work covered the main problematic areas: pay-cuts and wage setting; dismissal rules and destruction of jobs; flexible working time arrangements (bank of hours).

During the economic crisis the high cuts in the social benefits of households and the high rates of unemployment contributed mostly to reproduce the cycle of poverty in a very serious manner. The access and eligibility criteria to social benefits were endorsed and consequently the number of beneficiaries was reduced as well as the amounts received, as we can see from the latest study of EAPN Portugal.⁷ Social Insertion Income - Rendimento Social de Inserção (RSI) beneficiaries were reduced with more than 150,000 cases between 2010 and 2013 (in 2010 there were 525,723 beneficiaries and in 2013 were 360,235 beneficiaries). The average amount of benefit provided per beneficiary fell to 178.15€ in 2013 from about 189.52€ in 2010. The renewal of this provision must be requested by the beneficiaries, which in cases of forgetfulness or lack of knowledge, the recipients are automatically excluded from the measure. At the end of 2015, the number of

4 At the end of 2015, Portugal had the third highest public debt compared to GDP (128, 9%).

5 Children with special needs or disabilities have been particularly affected and the number of dropouts has increased. 38% (December 2013 to December 2014) lost social support. in OECD, 2014, Education Policy Outlook Portugal.

6 OECD, 2015, In It Together: Why Less Inequality Benefits All, OECD Publishing Paris.

7 EAPN Portugal study (2015) Social and institutional impact of economic and financial crisis in third sector organisations. For detail information about social benefits consult <http://www.seg-social.pt>

households who received the social insertion income was 134,161, with 295,668 beneficiaries. The average amount received by a beneficiary was 94.84€ and by a household was 213.89€.

Regarding the unemployment benefit, between 2010 and 2013, the number of unemployed increased from 424,966 to 562,998 and the amount of the benefit was reduced from 543.38€ to 534.83€. The access rules were changed in 2012;⁸ namely, a reduction in the period from 450 to 360 days and in the maximum amount of pay of €1,048 included no matter what the worker's salary was at the point of dismissal. Furthermore, a 10% cut in the amount of benefits was introduced, after six months of receiving the unemployment benefit.

Moreover, in the previous EAPN Portugal research about the social and institutional impact of the economic and financial crisis in Third Sector organisations, it is underlined that those organisations reported a significant increase of social vulnerability: individuals and families searching for social support; incidence of hunger cases among school children, householders with difficulties to pay support services to children and the elderly; increase of homelessness searching for support services and the increase of indebted households. At the end of 2011, the government introduced the Social Emergency Programme (Programa Social de Emergência),⁹ as a social response to reduce the social impact of the crisis through the provision of the 942 'social canteens' (up until that moment there were only 62) managed by social organisations to guarantee meals to the most vulnerable. EUR 50 million was provided for their creation. This measure came up at the same time as the much tighter control was implemented on access to social benefits such as the Social Insertion Income (RSI), the family allowance and the solidarity supplement for the elderly. As described above, this tightening of control led to a substantial fall of benefits paid out. The criticisms to the Social Emergency Programme were mainly that it should be an emergency measure, while it prevails as an assistance measure provided by social organisations.

Most indicators of the labour market and the social situation deteriorated with the unemployment rate reaching 16.7%, in 2013. Since then, it has been decreasing to 12.2% at the end of 2015.¹⁰ According to the Country Report Portugal 2016,¹¹ although it has been a recovery, the decrease of the active population due to the demographic and emigration trends explains also this fall. In 2014, the active population decreased 1, 2% (64,200 people) from the previous quarter (3rd lowest country among 28 Member States). Emigration flows reached 3.5% of approximately 10 million people during 2011 to 2013 (100,000 in 2011, 120,000 in 2012 and 128,000 in 2013). Emigration rates remained steady in 2014. Similar numbers can only be found in the 1960s, during the dictatorship and the colonial war. The qualified young people who emigrate due to the lack of jobs produced imbalances at the demographic level as well as in the contributions for social protection systems.

Moreover, in 2014 the ageing index was 141 elderly for 100 young people (Portugal has the 5th highest index among 28 Member States). The relative increase in ageing population associated with the working age population decrease brings important effects such as the increase of retirement age and increase of pensions' expenditures. In addition, the Portuguese birth rate is one of lowest in OECD countries.

As described in the Introduction the unemployment rate came to historical figures as well as youth unemployment which reached values close to 40% in 2013. In the last quarter of 2015, it amounted to 34.8%.¹² Regarding those under 25 years old, neither in employment, neither education, nor training (NEET) has also increased to levels around 14% of their age group (2013) having

8 Decree-Law n° 64/2012 of March (Decreto-Lei n° 64/2012, de 15 de Março)
http://www.dgap.gov.pt/upload/Legis/2012_dl_64_15_03.pdf

9 http://www.mercadosocialarendamento.msss.pt/programa_emergencia_social.jsp

10 According to INE data for the 4th quarter 2015

https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_indicadores&contecto=pi&indOcorrCod=0005599&selTab=tab0

11 http://ec.europa.eu/europe2020/pdf/csr2016/cr2016_portugal_en.pdf

12 http://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/---publ/documents/publication/wcms_412015.pdf

decreased to 12.3% in 2014. Unemployment is one of the biggest problems among young people under 25 years old. The crisis brought a new situation in which educated and skilled middle-class workers, mainly young, were affected by unemployment. This has created new patterns of poverty and inequality with special focus towards households where both parents became unemployed.

The Portuguese labour market is highly segmented due to a high number of temporary contracts (19% of total employees). Furthermore, most of the jobs created are based on temporary contracts. Between 2008 and 2012 the numbers increased for young people (15–24 years old) in the labour market on part-time jobs (10.4% and 20.1%), involuntary part-time jobs (42.2%; 45.5%) and in temporary employment (54.2% 56.5%)¹³.

The labour market reflects the deterioration in the working conditions that occurred in the last years, particularly for the young entrants regarding precarious forms of integration in the labour market and difficulties in achieving a stable job. The lower the age, the worse the working conditions are. And younger women are more affected by precariousness, e.g. part-time work and temporary contracts, than younger men. Differences by economic sector and company size are noticeable, with the services sector offering worse working conditions and the smaller companies offering more permanent jobs for young employees. In general, the working conditions of young entrants in the labour market have deteriorated in Portugal over the last five years, as a result of the effects of the crisis.¹⁴ Moreover, high levels of job destruction (more than 500,000 jobs were destroyed, between 2008 and 2013) have to be associated with the difficulty of young workers to enter the labour market.

1.1 The impact of the economic crisis viewed by Portuguese youth

Youth unemployment increased the average age of young people leaving the parental household in Portugal. In 2013 the average age was 29 years old (male (30.0) and female (28.0)) – while in the EU it was 26.1 years old (male (27.2) and female (25.0)).¹⁵

Living at home longer reflects the difficulty to get a job and live an independent life, as a source of fulfilment and professional identity which allows the transition to adulthood. According to the European Youth in 2016 report,¹⁶ 86% of Portuguese young people feel excluded due to the crisis. This is the second highest share in the EU 28 (average 57%) following Greece where the share with 93% is highest. Another relevant feature is the ‘enforced mobility’, as 41% of young people feel compelled to leave Portugal because of the crisis. With regard to the perception on the adequacy of the education system and the labour market demand, 61% of young people considered training, school and university education well adapted to the current working world (EU28 average 59%). The same report states that Portuguese young people’s participation in society is less than half of the young people surveyed¹⁷ that had voted in the previous three years (shares within the range of 44% to 49%). Broadly speaking, this may be linked with the loss of trust in the political system which is stated by the participants.

13 Eurofound, 2013, Working conditions of young entrants to the labour market p. 30

14 (<http://www.eurofound.europa.eu/observatories/eurwork/comparative-information/national-contributions/portugal/portugal-working-conditions-of-young-entrants-to-the-labour-market>) Published on: 08 January 2014

15 Being young in Europe Today, 2015, Eurostat, Children and young people in family and society, p. 44-47.

16 <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/atyourservice/en/20160504PVL00110/European-youth-in-2016>

17 Being young in Europe Today, 2015, Eurostat, page 62 (Flash Eurobarometer 375, titled ‘European youth: participation in democratic life’, which was conducted in 2013).

1.2 Material well-being and the subjective well-being of Portuguese citizens

The OECD report *How's Life in Portugal 2015*¹⁸ gives a picture of the *material well-being* and the *subjective well-being* of Portuguese citizens which seems in line with the social and economic description in the previous sections. Life satisfaction in Portugal is the second lowest in the OECD. Trust in other people lies below the European OECD average (5.3 while the European OECD average stands at 5.8).

The material well-being, since 2009, average Portuguese household disposable income fell notably and this led to a significant reduction (by 8.9%) in the poverty threshold¹⁹ which reflects the difficult economic conditions currently being faced. According to the Observatory of Education and Training Policies (Observatório de Políticas de Educação e de Formação) in 2014, the biggest problem of deprivation of families was the financial level (43.3% in food and essential goods), followed by leisure (29.4% without access to cultural activities and or sports), the social sector (26.4% in the frame, comfort - there are many children living alone with also small older brothers) and Education 25.8%).²⁰

Portugal has seen improvements in housing conditions, with the share of people living in dwellings with basic sanitation increasing. However, only 46.1% of Portuguese adults perceive their health as good or very good.²¹ In terms of educational attainment, between 2009 and 2013 the share of the adult working-age population with at least an upper secondary education increased by 10.2 percentage points to 40%. However, this is still far below the OECD average of 77.2%. Moreover, 55% of the adult population between 25-64 years old did not finished the secondary education level and 45% of the work force has few or no digital skills. 34.5% of young people with 15 years old repeated a school year (13% OCED average) according with data from PISA²² 2012. Graduate people 25-64 years old are still a low proportion (29th place within the 34 countries of OCDE). High level of drop rates and lower qualifications increases the youth unemployment and worsens the NEET rate.

To sum up, the Portuguese social and economic crisis context has translated into hard life conditions to the Portuguese and especially for the young people. Young unemployed people will speak by their own in the following pages on how the crisis has affected their lives.

18 <https://www.oecd.org/portugal/Better%20Life%20Initiative%20country%20note%20Portugal.pdf>

19 <http://www.eapn.pt/o-que-e-a-pobreza>: The European Union set up a calculation formula to define who was or not in poverty risk. The poverty line is defined as '60% of the median income per equivalent adult' (INE). Thus, it would be in poverty risk an adult who in 2014 had an income below 422 euros per month.

20 The State of Education in a State operated upon Portugal 2014 (O Estado da Educação num Estado Intervencionado Portugal 2014) Observatory of Education and Training Policies (Observatório de Políticas de educação e de Formação) p.11

21 http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/10665/170250/1/9789240694439_eng.pdf?ua=1&ua=1 World Health Statistics, 2015: Obesity rates among adults, self-reported (%): 15.4 in 2006 and 12.8 in 1999; Mortality from cardiovascular diseases (age-standardised rates per 100 000 pop.) 242.0 in 2012 and 424.9 in 2000; Mortality from cancer (age-standardised rates per 100 000 pop.) 200.7 in 2012 and 211.5 in 2000; Crude death rates for children (0–14 years old), (number of deaths per 100 000 children)2002 and 2012 Portugal (- 46 %) and the Crude death rates for young people (15–29 years old) (number of deaths per 100 000 young people) were seen in Portugal (- 53 %), Percent reduction in mortality rate of tuberculosis (among HIV negative people) a, 1990-2013, 58%

22 Programme for International Student Assessment

2. Theoretical and methodological approach

RE-InVEST aims to provide a philosophical, institutional and empirical foundation on the Social Investment Package, in order to enhance a more solidary, inclusive and trustful Europe. To reach this goal the theoretical and methodological approach proposed is through the intersection of capability and human rights approaches based on participatory action research.

The *Capability Approach* (CA) developed by Amartya Sen (1999) brought a new framework towards economic development by focusing his analysis on what people are able to be (or to do) to achieve their well-being or quality of life beyond income factors. So the core issue for Sen is not only what individuals choose, but the choices that they would make if they had the abilities/freedom to lead their lives the way they want to. Examples of capabilities can be: to be able to hold a decent job and not any job but a decent job; to be able to have leisure activities; to learn valuable things and be able to have education and be free of any kind of violence. So, quality of life does not depend only on income. Income is one of many variables, like trust in democracy, the political institutions in civil society, in the neighbourhood and in the household. In addition, the CA has an intrinsic value quite different from the practical approach more concerned with the economic growth, GDP, which potentially generates decent jobs. Speaking about human dignity and about what people consider they need and should have is very important to diagnosis social impacts on vulnerable people: ‘What am I able to do and be?’

The *Capability Approach* as developed by Sen (1999) and Nussbaum (2011) defines the person’s wellbeing in terms of beings and doings (achievements/functionings) a person achieves and her/his capability to choose among different combinations of such functionings. Functionings may be considered the basic needs as having shelter, health care, education or more complex features such as self-respect and well-being. To live a life that persons want to lead and have reason to value, the resources and conversion factors are central components (Figure 2.1.) In other words, the perception that the individual has of the quality of life depends not only on his personality or features like age or gender, but also on the resources available and the cultural values of the society where he/she is living in.

So, resources can be defined as material conditions such as income, goods and services, which have an instrumental value and are the means needed to reach functionings. Conversion factors help to convert resources into doing and wellbeing. There are a range of conversion factors: personal, social and environmental that can constrain or enable people’s capabilities. Personal conversion factors are such as skills and body features; social conversion factors are like social norms, laws, customs and traditions and social institutions and policies; finally environmental conversion factors are such as climate and geography. The achieved functionings are the way people live to be free to be able to choose things to value in life e.g. to be able to choose a decent job.

Figure 2.1 Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings

Capabilities and human rights are directly linked by describing the core values of well-being and a good life. Besides, human rights have been developed strongly in the past century. In the 20th century key international human rights instruments were established, namely: the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) adopted by the United Nations in 1948 which states in Article 25 that ‘Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and the necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of live hood in circumstances beyond his control’. In the international and national legal framework of UDHR, the states are obliged to ensure the effective exercise of the right to protection against poverty and social exclusion. As it is pointed out in the Council of Europe Revised European Social Charter, Article 30, the States must take measures ‘to promote the effective access of persons who live or risk living in a situation of social exclusion or poverty, as well as their families, to, in particular, employment, housing, training, education, culture and social and medical assistance’.

Human rights are inalienable rights and fundamental entitlements by a human being as prepolitical status prior membership to a state. The Human Rights approach includes a universal and holistic perspective of the human being in terms of civil and political rights and the social and economic rights. They set up the standard of living conditions and the deprivation of needs can be as a denial of rights. In this context the Human rights discourse can emancipate and transform through collective action and participation of who is excluded by their own rights.

The Merging of Knowledge (MOK) approach involves a collective of mixed groups of researchers the co-construction of knowledge about poverty and social exclusion by discussion and reflection: people who experience poverty and social exclusion in first hand to talk about their needs. To bring a more complete and broader knowledge it is crucial to have their participation and their own voice as co-constructors of Knowledge. Academics and scholars should assume the role to them to ‘*Explain to us rather, Help us to think*’. This process helps to raise awareness about their situation of rights denial and implies to the solution of the problem and policy recommendations. The knowledge of social workers who work with vulnerable people is a core part of the MOK perspective (figure 2).

Figure 2.2 The merging of knowledge

RE-InVEST research approach is a Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA) developed in seven steps (Toolkit, 44-45):

1. identify and meet partner NGO/gatekeeper,;
2. preliminary 'meet ups' (for trust building if necessary);
3. first meeting with participants – trust building;
4. developmental: implement developmental human rights & capability approach;
5. inquiry/data gathering;
6. identifying patterns (key issues and themes of concern to the group) and;
7. undertake action/outcome using one or a combination of approaches.

According to the Portuguese context (see Section 1) we decided to work with ten young unemployed people (aged 18 and 29; 2 males and 8 females), from an urban area: S. João da Madeira, Aveiro district (see Appendix 1 for the profile participant group description). The 'Youth Association of Urban Echoes' (Associação de Jovens Ecos Urbanos) <http://www.ecosurbanos.pt/organizacao/> was the gatekeeper (step 1). It is a grassroots organisation which works with young people in poverty and social exclusion and is a member of EAPN Portugal. This status made the process quicker by explaining the aims of the project and the role of the NGO and the selection of the vulnerable group (step 2).

In November of 2015 three meetings were held at Ecos Urbanos office (19, 24 and 26 November) in order to have the group formed (step 3). In the first meeting only three females attended, in the second meeting 7 young people participated and the third meeting was attended by 10 persons. There were three brief meetings with those responsible at the NGO to discuss and to find solutions to overcome the low attendance, namely to pay the lunch and offer a coffee-break per meeting to each person; these offers were based on having the vulnerable situation in mind that we were dealing with. During the first meeting the aim of the project was presented, after the participants had introduced themselves. Furthermore, the principles of participation were discussed, namely the guarantee of confidentiality and anonymity during all the research stages. Participants filled in an applicant form which stated the confidentiality of data collected. Participants also consented to record the sessions. Last, but not least, as a first approach to freely debated youth unemployment, each of the participants made a drawing about the impacts of unemployment (feelings, attitudes, consequences) on their lives, and shared its meanings. (see Appendix 2).

The next meeting took place with 7 new persons (who met during lunch time which created a good atmosphere) to whom we briefly explained the aims of the project. In the meeting we started with a dynamic introduction of the participants (ice-break) each saying his/her name and one characteristic they like most to create trust. Then we proceeded with the drawing methodology (Appendix 2).

The last meeting in November allowed for the ten new participants to meet during lunchtime where we informally spoke about RE-InVEST, before the ice-break activity took place. Afterwards each participant showed his or her drawing and explained the meaning of it. Furthermore, the meanings were discussed and participants reflected on those features and assessed the way how the meeting went.

'Freehand Drawing' enabled participants to express visually their present constraints and future challenges about being unemployed through image interpretation and discussion, and encouraged a reflexive engagement to generate alternative perspectives.

There were more four group meetings with ten participants that took place in November, December 2015 and January 2016 with the aim to implement the developmental human rights and capability approach (step 4), inquiry/data gathering (step 5).

After discussing, reflecting and sharing feelings, attitudes and the impacts of unemployment in their well-being, the group put a great emphasis on debating about solutions for unemployment rather than focusing on the difficulties faced by the lack of work. Accordingly, a brainstorm about Rights, Trust and future plans was carried out. To deepen the social diagnosis, two focus groups were created on the living conditions and how they affect their quality of life. The group was subdivided according to the education level.

The focus group about income and living conditions was inspired on 'The Survey on Income and Living Conditions, conducted in 2015 over the previous year's income, information of INE, 18 December 2015

(https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_destaques&DESTAQUESdest_boui=224739104&DESTAQUESmodo=2).

With respect to data gathering, we use the toolkit (page 62) 'snake' timetable as a way of undertaking personal testimonies, by biographical memory as well as a collective exercise concerning the austerity measures and the social and economic indicators implemented in Portugal during the last ten years (see Appendix 3,4 and5).

Moreover, biographical storytelling was applied voluntarily by two participants, guided by recommended prompts from the toolkit (page 51-53) to the interview guide by the facilitator based on the: individual impacts of the crisis/changes in functionings in their individual lives; emotional/immaterial/feelings/dignity; collective trust and participation, these inform about changes at community level and changes in capabilities. The group listened and commented on the testimonies, which was a first step in identifying matters of main concern for the group as well as to identify recommendations (step 6).

The steering committee was composed of two members of the focus group, one researcher and the executive director of 'Youth Association of Urban Echoes'. They met in May 2016 main findings of the present report. It will be extended to social workers of other local NGOs which work with the group. The 'action' part of the PAR approach through rights action and MOK approaches will be implemented in the next stage of the RE-InVEST project as agreed by the Consortium. PAR implies to engage testimonies who experience social problems and work in order to find their own solutions. Agency was discussed at the first meetings and some proposals came out in the group without practical effects yet, such as: manifesto about youth unemployment to be presented to the city council (proposed by a person that in the meantime found a job); the right to work was introduced but it was pointed out that the core question is to find strategies to face unemployment which is not the aim of the project. The agency element will be a crucial point to work towards in the following group meetings.

3. Two selected biographies

3.1 First biography

I have a nursing degree and my life now is like this: if I choose the easiest way, which at the same time is very difficult, I have to emigrate. ... but it is hard to move to another country. I already had job proposals from Norway, Belgium, Germany, UK ... thousands of them. It is easy! I have lots of colleagues that went abroad. The process is to fill in all the bureaucratic documents and wait for their call. (...) But it is difficult ...I'm not a person who gives up! We hear all the time that this is bad. There are nursing strikes...it is bad, it is bad... but I cannot say that it is, if I don't try. ... But then I think 'should I stay here unemployed, attending training courses to improve the CV...Here the job's proposals require young people with lots of experience. Because of this I feel frustrated...then I think I will stay here doing volunteer work in nursing... it will be open a nursing department in the Red Cross ... but when I think more and more about the access conditions to go to the UK, one day they will be changed and the Nurses Order will demand more exams from January next year.. .and at the same time the agency's calling all the time to start the process now ... So to emigrate is becoming more and more a strong option.'

B finished her nursing degree and she is unemployed. She feels confused whether to emigrate or to stay in the country. Once forced to go abroad to have a job, she will not come back to Portugal, it will be only the country where she was born which makes her sad. With the age of 23, she pointed out that she will find a good job abroad, she will marry there, and she will have a house and a family. In the end she will build her life there, ... *'It won't be the same as my father who was forced to migrate to Angola due to the economic crisis and will return after saving some money.'* In her point of view young people should be able to choose to live in their own country but the economic crisis forces them to emigrate. The low wages are very discouraging after investing in her education. She states that there is a shortage of nurses in health services but there are no job proposals.

She tries to not give up: *'But then there's that feeling that things will change and if there is a nursing shortage it is because they need them! We have to give it time but waiting is discouraging and begins to be tiring.'*

In 2010 when she was attending secondary school she started thinking about a nursing career:

It was a valued job, so I was enthusiastic about it. I didn't have financial difficulties. In 2011 I joined the nursing college. That year TROIKA came and the subsequent measures, my father began to have difficulties in finding work (construction sector), in paying taxes... and the family/children allowance and scholarship were cut. Because of that, my father found himself in need to migrate to Angola, leaving me and my brothers behind and on our own.'

B is doing volunteering work in the local Red Cross as a way to help people in need and feel useful but she doesn't trust social public services. She has a negative view of the public servants of the social security. When her father asked for social support:

The lady (Social Security) told my father: You are not poor.' I am not poor but I'm in economic difficulties, it's just me to care for three children. I want to know why you are withdrawing the support now when I need it most. The woman said, 'Let me see: you own a house, right? Sell it and you won't need to go abroad.' It makes no sense. For the social security employee we had to sell the house as a way to prevent us from emigrating. They don't want to know. They know that people go through difficulties but they don't care about people's problems. So my advice is to go to social organisations. For example the Red Cross that cares, that take time to listen to your story ...That's their mission and do not want anything for it... They have many volunteers from social, health areas ... They listen to your story and will try to help you.'

With her father in Angola she has to be strong and resilient and should not give up in hard times to end the higher education program and care for her brothers:

'It was a tough year for adaptation and the combination of studies/family, because the father's absence was noticeable. It was difficult to adapt...for me and for my brothers. We have to handle everything but I realised that I could not give up. My father was doing that for me. I endeavoured more. I finished my degree. At this point we were in economic constraints and we did not receive support.'

In 2014, B witnessed the deterioration of the health cuts in people's lives and how this worsened the working conditions of health professionals during her internship in public health care:

'One of the most significant memories I have during the internship was the fatigue and overwork of the health professionals, which conditioned the quality of care. Also I witnessed in Psychiatry an increasing number of admissions of people with academic training e.g. nurses, doctors, and lawyers, due to depression.'

3.2 Second biography

Z has her life routine very scheduled during her twenty four years' life time. She attended vocational training on events organisation to get the secondary level. The grades to go to college were not good enough and she had to give up of high education due to economic reasons. Dropping out of school made her losing her family allowance what does not make any sense to her. It made things even worse. Afterwards she got temporary jobs: the longest period was nine months and the shortest was one week: *'From June 2011 to December 2015, I was employed one year and eleven months and have been unemployed during two years and five months.'* Z worked in different sectors and developed different skills: in restaurants, in textile factories; in a train company and grape harvests. In between she attended training with an average duration of 50 hours per training: first aid in geriatrics; first aid hydrotherapy; child health care; Portuguese traditional cuisine; and HACCP.²³ She goes fortnightly to temporary employment agencies to renew her information and asking if there is a job for her. The same effort B uses towards the employment centre, but she has not succeeded:

'I went this morning to know my situation, if everything was all right...if there was any labour supply...The employment servant simple said 'Go to the website and see'. It is the second time they gave me the same answer.'

During the economic crisis her mother was dismissed after working many years in textile factories. Z said that several textile factories closed in the area and many people lost their jobs. Once in a while her mother does undeclared work but very seldom. Z cannot count on her because she has financial problems too. During 2013, the family environment got worse and Z was victim of domestic violence by her mother. Their relation is characterised with bad and not so bad moments. Nonetheless, in 2014, Z was unemployed and moved from her place of birth to live with her boyfriend. During last year he also became unemployed with no right to social benefit because his employer did not pay social security, something of which he was completely unaware. For a while he worked in a restaurant and was dismissed. During that period in which both were unemployed, she received unemployment benefit (around 350€ per month until November 2015 to pay all the bills). After that she had no money and asked for social support:

'I can apply for the social insertion income in March. Before that I can't have it because I have received unemployment benefits, so I am not entitled to receive it. They ask for last three months bank account... She tried different sorts to get financial support: I resorted to banks, friends, acquaintances and family. All refused. I ask for food assistance in social canteens. They just gave me an option: go to the social canteen if I want it! (...) I'll get lunch and dinner every day, at the time they want, and the food most of the time is cold. The food containers (...) spoiled ... and I don't have microwave to heat the food and it goes like ice cold for the 'little mouth ...'

²³ Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point

Z and her boyfriend live in an old house with poor conditions with rain coming through the roof, and the walls have dampness. Z and her boyfriend do not have money to pay for gas or heater:

'If we use the heater then the electricity bill is expensive. The washing machine is from the landlady and is broken. And she won't fix it. I do the laundry in the tank by hand. The landlady has to do works on the roof... but she doesn't want to do anything (...) and when it rains, it rains inside the house.'

Without financial support Z cannot pay health exams: I don't need to pay health taxes but I have to do exams that are not covered by the National Health System and those I have to pay. My boyfriend is ill on an arm and has to do exams which costs 80€ but we don't have money to pay and we don't have any help. She felt discriminated when goes to hospital services: if you are a person with money, you are well treated. In my home town I had no complain, here I have.

As already stated, her parents got divorced when she was a baby:

'My father left me with two months...never supported me. He is abroad I don't know anything about him. I'm his daughter and I went to court a few years ago to have some financial allowance. Regarding to family support she pointed out the fact of being victim of domestic violence: If I tell my story, you stay open-mouthed. The mother who beats her own daughter...I let it happen twice, the third...I did not let her do it again and I slammed against the wall, with my grandmother watching... I called the police.'

With regards to family ties, Z added that the death of her aunt was a great loss. She had the reference role in her life:

'I cook very well because I learned with my aunt. My family says that I'm very like her...she died when I was twelve years old.'

In her words, *friends' emotional support is more important than any other kind of family support.*

She has a group of friends who meet across the country to play arrows; sometimes they friendly pay a drink, because she does not have money. This good atmosphere is essential to avoid depression:

'(...) Because of that (domestic violence), last year I had two depressions one after another and the doctor says if I stay like that I'm going to have another one. I take four different pills per day. If weren't my friends ...With my mother not so much, we had our peaks. But now friends, that's why I like to play arrows ...'

Z's level of trust in social organisations is very low because she felt nobody helped her. As she is in need, she is deeply against the refugee aid. Firstly, the welfare state should ensure social rights for national citizens before providing all kind of rights to the newcomers:

'My boyfriend is trying to get health care for free. And we can't benefit from any of that. You don't have no rights to social security, employment centre, has nothing...I also go to Syria (...) and then I come back... Why don't they go to the richest countries nearby? They have no crises...it has small crises...If I have 5 or 10 thousand euros for a trip to Greece...they have more money than us.'

One important feature that enables her to move on was when she took the driver's license in 2010. As future plans her dream is: *to work in the company that manages the arrows championships.*

4. Analysis

The current data analysis results from the empirical study based upon the participatory action research. The discussions of the focus groups were recorded and transcribed and the content analysis²⁴ was elaborated according to the two main research questions pointed out by Reinvest:

1. the crisis has negative social consequences which undermined the human rights of vulnerable groups;
2. the negative social consequences lead to a growing distrust and loss of solidarity.

The priority issues linked with the first hypothesis that came out from young unemployed testimonies were dimensions such as: education (Section 4.1.1), employment (Section 4.1.2), social protection (Section 4.1.3); health (Section 4.1.4), and housing (Section 4.1.5). In what concerns to (dis)trust young unemployed people emphasised this subject towards neighbours (Section 4.2.1) and family (Section 4.2.2), social organisations (Section 4.2.3), public services like social security (Section 4.2.4) and public employment service (Section 4.2.4), political institutions (Section 4.2.5) their opinion about refugees (4.2.6) and the meaning of Human Rights (4.2.7).

4.1 The social consequences of the crisis on human rights of young unemployed

4.1.1 Education level and labour market opportunities

The participant group is composed by members who have a degree and who attended basic and secondary school.²⁵ For both, to have a high education degree is perceived as very important to get a better job: *'More studies you have, more chances you will have to find a job.'* The education level will influence the future standard of well-being: *'I think it enhances the long-term quality of life.'* Nonetheless, educational choices are strongly shaped by the labour market pressure and household economic resources. On one hand, who have low qualifications didn't pursue their education for economic reasons and opted for attending vocational training to raise their job opportunities: *'I studied to the 9th grade but couldn't attend school to the 12th year. At that time there was no money to go to school.'* In addition some low skilled participants wish to attend university studies: *'I hope to work two years to earn some money and then go to university or work at the same time.'* On the other hand, who has a degree reported economic difficulties to finish their academic studies. One participant stopped studying one year to help their parents in a small family company and she has to apply for a bank credit to pay tuition fees: *'... the last year was very complicated in this aspect. I cannot invest in training, postgraduate courses and seminars. Turns out to be more difficult to invest on it ...'* Another participant emphasised that her father had to immigrate to Angola to help financing her studies. A third young female had a scholarship from the State, otherwise her parents couldn't afford it. In her case the lack of money doesn't allow her to

24 The content analysis are based on all sessions developed, recorded, and transcribed, which includes the visual methods, like drawings, snakes individual interviews, interviews in depth. From the main and repeated topics were organised in main categories and subcategories.

25 As it can be seen in annex 1 from the eleven participants three have master degree – nursing; psychology; biology - (female); four have 12th level, attended training courses/ secondary education - Beauty treatments and massage; laboratory analysis; on events organisation (female); one has 11th level; and three have 9th level – (2 male and 1 female).

move to a big city like Lisbon to look for a job more suitable to her qualification. Furthermore, they are aware of some study areas such as engineer or sciences that will increase more labour opportunities rather than humanities. In this sense, education plays an instrumental role in fostering economic growth, instead of well-being and social development as reported by young unemployed.

Having in mind the relation between education level and labour opportunities, for the **qualified participants** - that never worked before - there is an obvious imbalance between supply and demand in labour market and therefore there are too many qualified unemployed people for few jobs available. In the participants' opinions this devalues the qualifications and in this sense: '*... it is not a guarantee of work ...*' Moreover, the three master degrees unemployed female considered themselves to be overqualified to get unskilled jobs like in shopping stores: '*... I am overqualified for some things and for other I don't have experience.*' At the same time, when they apply for a job, employers require work experience. Such requirement undermines the right to work:

'... Without an opportunity how we can gain experience? The employers and society must be aware to give an opportunity to young people who don't have experience but have lots of energy, lots of ideas and we need to show that we are dynamic and not passive.'

From the point of view of **those with few qualifications** considered themselves as underqualified. The majority of them have attended vocational training to get the secondary school as a way to raise their opportunities to entry in the labour market: '*It was one reason why I attended professional training.*'

In the line of capability approach what real opportunities and freedom youth unemployment participants have to achieve education that they can have reason to value? The few jobs available limit individual choices to the ones that potentially will have more opportunities and not the ones they felt are reasonable to live: '*Today I feel that young people chose a degree not because they like it, but because they expect to get a job. It isn't an option it is a need felt by parents who pay our education.*' Furthermore, participants as young unemployed felt social pressure to not stop '*... and attending training courses to fill in a CV...*'

In this sense, young people 'felt obliged' to choose a degree according with labour market needs in first place instead of fighting for their individual wishes and dreams: '*We should think very carefully about the areas which will give employment and opt for that.*' Even being aware of the permanent change in labour market: (...) '*I chose sciences which had more opportunities. Six years later, after graduating, I realise that it's the same. Maybe it is more difficult than working as a kindergarten teacher.*' There is the perception that the economy encourages the 'practical and objective tasks' rather than reflexive ones:

'... We have to think more in practical education ... what do a philosopher does? Will teach, will write books, while an engineer knows what will work for a company like engineer... practical things, objective things. I think increasingly, the practical work is valued more than the broad knowledge degrees.'

Portugal never had before a high level of graduate population as nowadays. Nonetheless, considering the overall population it remains to make an effort to ensure high education for all and to improve the high figures of school dropout. In this sense, in one participant words, being the first household member attending college was always felt as a family dream and a way of changing life for better far from the parents' working class background. This expectation fulfilled as a fundamental assumption of democratic societies where school performed a key role of social mobility and work status. However, under the current hardest circumstances, to find a job is a 'postponed dream':

'I believed so. Now I don't know. (...) To have a degree ... it would be that change. They (parents) didn't have the opportunity to study but we were going to have. And now I see I finished higher education and after all ... nothing changed that much ... And that of course worries me.'

4.1.2 Quality jobs and decent work

The employment status of the young unemployed households are broadly speaking blue-collar jobs and temporary jobs or on social protection benefits and in kind support (see annex 1 profile participant group). We are dealing with a vulnerable group with low income which constrain the different dimensions of life, including education and leisure.

The economic crisis deteriorated the right to have a decent job. The construction sector was one of most affected by the crisis in Portugal: *'...when Troika came, my father was a self-employed worker...and he had to cancel social security to not pay, otherwise he didn't have money. Everything was still (construction sector) he couldn't find work ...'* Before the crisis was easier to find employment in blue-collar jobs: *'...even in the factories... my father was taking many jobs and he was getting little time to do other things (...) and from 2009, 2010 (...) wasn't like that.'* The job losses, the raise of unemployment to historical figures and the bad working conditions (low wages, 9, 10 working hours per day) leads to a common feeling of how difficult it is to find work within the current economic and social context. Job searching make people feel frustrated (see annex 2 Drawing). The skilled work is devalued: *'(...) it is not as valued... I think it has deteriorated. The conditions in dignity have worsened.'* and there is a feeling of unfairness having in mind the relation between high qualifications and low wages: *'We invest so much... and I see minimum wage proposals and I do not think it's fair that kind of salary for skilled labour (...) it is revolting. It makes us also refuse it.'*

In the participant's words, the huge imbalance between demand and offer of the labour market, allow employers to choose very qualified persons paying low wages. The job criteria selection became who accepts the lowest wage: *'I think they (employers) are taking advantage of the fact that we need to get work ... few proposals, I see two in per month or not even that.'* There is a common feeling of having no choice by accepting the employers' offers in a way that they play the rules of labour market conditions. Younger employed people are mostly in precarious work, poorly paid, insecure and unprotected. This kind of behaviour can lead to exploitation and discrimination from employers and increases competition for the few jobs available among. Young people have few opportunities to enter the workforce. When they have the opportunity to start their professional life, the qualified jobs are paid as no skilled jobs:

'...who has just come out of the university will earn the same as those who work in a factory. I have a friend who is working in a car factory and earns €680; I have friend who is an architect in internship and gets €550; and I know a mechanical engineer who earns €700; and I know that if I get a job is going to be around €650, €700 ...'

In the participants' opinion graduates and young professionals such as engineers from environmental, electrical, mechanical areas are low paid, receiving around 700€. 800€ is considered by the labour market as the maximum. The current amount paid on the traineeships of the job centre is 650€ and research grants wages are €755/degree and masters €980 (gross salary), stated the participants.

In the graduated unemployed participants' opinion, skilled labour was well paid in the past compared to today. Nowadays, the wages amounts are very similar to those paid in shops or factories, where workers usually have the 9th or 12th school level. For the young undergraduate unemployed participants the effective working conditions in blue collars jobs are as well badly paid: *'2, 88 €/hour in a factory.'* with long working hours:

'...8, 9, and 10 hours a day ...' and with bad working environment: '... people are very rude. For example the factory where my mother works, people do not talk to each other.' It is also: *'very precarious ...'* It is given an example: *'At the factory (x) we work during a week and in the next week or a month they no longer want you...'*

Besides the low wages, precarious jobs is the only experience some participants, who have worked before, have: *'Since I finished my studies until now, it has been 23 months working and 29 months unemployed (...) I had five or six jobs...the last one was nine months.'* Nowadays precariousness starts to be a common place, far from the idea of a lifelong job as happened in the past:

'I think there's really much more precarious work, three, six contracts a year at most, for our age as far as I know. (...) I have a colleague of mine who got signed at a shopping store for six months, after six months was renewed and after the end of more six months they renewed.'

The rise of precarious work is linked somehow to the way economy is working: *'There is so much job rotation (...) because the businesses are also not healthy ...'* The fixed terms contracts allow employers easy dismissals: *'...There is more supply. Employers say ok: 'if this employee doesn't fit we have to look for another. (...) It is bad for the people (...) only serves the employer not the employee.'*

In some cases due to the hard conditions to get the first job, it is stated that young people do voluntary work by despair as a way to enter the labour market:

'...we can talk about companies that want volunteer interns and they end up taking advantage of the despair of the younger, I cannot even consider as employment conditions because this is not employment.'

The well-being was put into question at the workplace due to the rising level of unemployment:

'on the different places where I worked in, I felt that after 2008 it has been more distrust which undermines interpersonal relations, between colleagues due the insecurity felt by the possibility of becoming unemployed. Even the job situation isn't the most desirable it is better to have a job and feel uncomfortable rather than to be unemployed.'

The unemployed nurse mentioned the shortage of qualified personnel at the health services, which contrasts to the huge number of qualified unemployed people with no opportunity to work:

'... It scares me to hear the news that there are shortages of qualified personnel, ... They just take advantage of them as volunteers with no guarantee of staying. What happens is that, when they finish their volunteering work, they leave the country ...They (foreign recruitment agencies) come to us and give us exciting proposals. I speak on behalf of myself, I have turned down some proposals and the way to pull over is, "we feel insecure in getting home or ..." and they say: "We find it!"'

The right to have a job is deeply deteriorated as far as unemployed young people are concerned to get their first job: *'The hardest is to get a job without experience...And we don't have experience.'* Young unemployed participants argue that it must be given more opportunities to young people and believe in their capabilities. They ask how can we have experience if we just finished secondary school or college? *'... Experience is study, is that it? I wasn't born knowing everything. People have the first job... they need to have it...if it is the first job there isn't experience, we have to begin from somewhere. A person was not born an expert.'* In the same line of thought, it is once more emphasised that young unemployed are excluded from job opportunities when work experience is required: *'... I see a lot of offers that ask, 5, 2, 3 years' experience ... for a person who has just come out of a higher education institution it is impossible ...'* In addition, even working in less qualified jobs are not accepted because they also haven't experience: *'(...) I went to an interview at a store and the lady liked me (...) but I had no experience.'*

With the recent historical high unemployed rates (17% in 2013) were simultaneously recorded high emigration rates which have remained steady last few years (2013/14). This data can be reported by the participants' testimonies: *'My family emigrated because they had no jobs here'; '...my father felt compelled to emigrate...to Angola.'* Having in mind the pressure of the emigration issue to find a job, it was deeply discussed among participants whether it could be considered as a free option or to what extent could be faced as an enforced decision. Some of them definitely did not want to emigrate and it is assumed to not leave the country where they were born: *'I don't feel like leaving Portugal.'* Other participant wants to go abroad only for leisure time and to know different cultures: *'I'd like to do an exchange (...) I would enjoy doing it but not to work.'* Another participant assumed that: *'If we do not have opportunities here we have to try outside.'* Others would rather prefer to emigrate if they have money for the travels expenses and for the first period of time to find a job. The discussion about a wider European economic crisis came into question once it is not just a national issue but a global concern. In young people opinion's the nature of the current emigration trends were also debated:

Portugal will become the place where I was born. It won't be like my father that emigrate to earn money and will come back. I and my generation will go to live a life there... I will get a job, I will marry there I will have a house and raise my children I won't come back.'

To emigrate remains a difficult decision even when they have a good job proposal because it also means leaving their families.

4.1.3 Social Protection

To what extent social rights are met during the social and economic crisis? To what extent social policies tackle and prevent the disadvantage people to escape from poverty and social exclusion and promote the right to live a life with in dignity? As showed in part 1 the austerity measures deteriorated the Welfare State and strongly affected social benefits like the unemployment; the social insertion income. According to the participants' words social investments are replaced for neo liberal policies: *'The State cuts the protection to people in need to give to those who do not need, you know! That's a bit stupid.'*; *'It (the State) gives banks and cuts us for instances ...'* The financial crisis is explained by bankruptcy and by the State helping the banks system: *'had loans from banks either way (...) the State cannot have money for everything (...) the responsibility was accumulated by many years. It has been created a hole that now has to solve.'*

During the economic crisis many families felt their social situation changed dramatically and try to apply for the social insertion income but the eligibility conditions became very restrict:

'What I mean is that once everything was fine, we had no financial difficulties and they gave us support (family allowance; user fees, scholarships) when my father went (to Angola) and we need support they withdraw everything. My father will come back and maybe we will receive again. It doesn't makes any sense.'

The social benefits cuts in the social insertion income and the strict rules to access it are viewed as unfair:

'It was stupid because it had to do with the (...) bank accounts, I have with my sister money in a bank account due to scholarships (...) in case of being necessary to help my parents and it was mainly to pay for home, the fees...'

Indeed, young unemployed people reported that there were cuts in social benefits with the economic crisis:

'Yes, there are always cuts. My scholarship in the first year (2010) was higher than in the subsequent years. My parents received the social insertion income there was a time it went down a bit.'(...) *'My colleagues ran out of scholarships for debts that they didn't know they had to the Social Security for example ...'*

One participant asked for that benefit but it wasn't approved:

'They ask for the last three months of the bank account and I received the partial unemployment benefit which was €380 ... My boyfriend has been unemployed for a year and also has no right.'

In addition, the conditionality of the social income benefits produce the risk of restrained incentives to take up work:

'There are things we want to do but we can't. For example we have the House of Creativity when there are events, to point the way to people. It is only possible to do some casual work with green receipts but this puts into question other types of support. It is to pay to work ...'

Furthermore, it was stated that before the troika the social benefits were higher than during the adjustment period:

'Everyone does not like Socrates but the minimum wage was the minimum wage. My parents were both unemployed and we survived. Subsidies were higher, unemployment benefits were higher.'

There are two participants who benefit from daily food support from social canteens (Social Emergency Programme (Programa Social de Emergência)) provided by social organisations. One of the participants stated that the meals have good quality, and some elements agreed that the social organisation in question is considered as having a good service. The other beneficiary claimed quite the opposite: cold food delivered in spoiled recipients. This matter was discussed among the group and the answer of the different social organisations to this particular regard.

All participants have some kind of social support due to their vulnerable context: family allowance; social minimum income; unemployed benefits; scholarships. The amount of the benefits was reduced during the economic crisis. For more detail information see the annex 1.

4.1.4 Health status of participants and medical care provision

The scope of the relatives' diseases are very linked with the unemployed effects, as a multidimensional phenomenon that affects several dimensions of the human well-being (even there is not a linear relation between causes and consequences) like depression, domestic violence and divorce as well as health problems spread among family members:

'My mother was unemployed (...) and the depression that she had due to domestic violence became worse. (...) She has problems at physical level that will not let her work. Sometimes to do easy things and she looks like an old lady of 80 years and she is only 40. (...) My younger brother after the separation of my parents became very psychologically affected... he was born with a mental disorder... He has to have more support in school (...) my sister is celiac.'

The health expenses are a burden to the family budget, and the money available is driven to the priorities:

'My sister is celiac; it is very difficult because the medicines to the disease are very expensive. My brother needs a medicine every day for his concentration. In that house everyone needs something...it is complicated. We have to choose to help one at a time... and then the others are deprived. We can't cope with everything.'

There are cases in vulnerable conditions which are due to the fact that there is no money to pay exams: *'... my boyfriend is waiting to take a medical exam to the arm but there is no money.'*

Finally, dental care is the most needed among the group, because isn't covered by National Health System NHS.

Regarding to the perception about medical care provided, indeed, there is a favourable opinion towards the NHS. From one participant's opinion, it was not felt any change in her treatment and in her mother's, before and during the crisis in terms of access to medical consultations or fees. Another participant pointed out that even health services contacted her mother to go to routine consultations. In this sense, for an unemployed graduated nurse, the NHS improved considerably for the last forty years: *'I think Portugal has given more and more emphasis to health care, primary care, (...) and I think there have been major improvements ...'* A different perspective is stated by other testimonies that do not have money to spend in doctors due to the high cost compared to their strict budgets. One participant mentioned a discriminated treatment regards who doesn't have money or social status:

'Here at São João (Hospital) it seems that it depends on the person you are. If you are a person with possessions are well treated, here I have reasons to complain ...'

In the next lines it will be given a picture of the health system through two testimonies of the group (a nurse and a clinical psychologist) during their internship in 2014. Those voices translate the negative impacts of the austerity measures in the health of the Portuguese citizens as mentioned in part 1 (national context) regards to the increase of the fees in the emergency services; the shortage of health professionals and the deterioration of quality of the care.

The increase of the emergency fees makes harder the access of the most vulnerable people to health care. Moreover it is noticed that there has been cuts in health under the effectiveness discourse and attempt to maintain the same services, with a reduction of the health professionals:

'Providing the services but without increasing the costs ... so I think that it shouldn't be cut back on staff even if the answer is fast, is effective ...'

This affects the quality of care:

'... There are people who are fortunate enough to go on the right day, at the right time and they are cared for, in my opinion, are better cared for than others in most troubled times.'

'...There is a shortage of nurses and of doctors...They worked exaggerated shifts to ensure services, they felt really tired. (...) there were nurses who worked afternoons, nights and in the following day started on the afternoon...'

The payment of overtime is covered by the 'bank of hours'. They didn't receive and then they were revolted. They worked, and worked and didn't receive by doing emergency services. Those hard working conditions led some of those professionals to depression:

'... In psychiatric services... people with depression are more and more graduated... in my time (internship) were there two nurses with depression ...by excess of work.'

To sum up in the participant words:

'It is very difficult to maintain a good level of productivity, not only productivity in terms of results but productivity in terms of the quality of what is done ...'

4.1.5 Housing conditions of participants

As education, employment and health, housing is an important dimension when talking about the social damages of the crisis among the young unemployed. They reported some housing problems mainly dampness, missing heating conditions and no money to pay the rent. Regarding dampness four participants stated to have it in their homes: *'...Dampness. It was horrible my father every year had to paint the room. It was all black.'* Concerning the heating conditions, the heater is only used in a part of the house: *'...My mom warms the room and then heats the rooms when we go there.'* Or even avoid its use: *'... We use the heater and then the electricity is expensive ...'* One participant mentioned having no heater and another one said that: *'In January and February I have to go to my father's house because of the cold weather.'*

Regarding the issue of having washing machine all participants said that they had, except one: *'The washing machine is from the landlady and is broken. And she doesn't want to fix it. I do the wash by hand.'* The same participant emphasised do not have gas for heating food and the house also needs improvements: *'The landlady has to do works on the roof... but she doesn't want to do anything (...) and it rains inside the house because of the damages on the roof.'*

What concerns to pay the rent, four participants can pay with their household's income and another four have social support to do it. One of the participants emphasised that even having social support it is difficult to manage to pay the bills:

'... There are months that for having water, electricity, my mother has to ask for help to my older brother who doesn't live with us but that sometimes has to help otherwise would be complicated.'

Another one reported that though they can pay the rent with her mother's salary: *'...there is a very small amount left over.'*

When questioned about the possibility of affording a week's vacation over the past decade with all the expenses paid, the majority of the participants mentioned that they don't afford money for holidays. One participant takes vacations with the help of relatives: *'(...) in that period both were*

employed without large incomes but we could go. Since 2009 with the situation of my parents, we go but we don't pay all things.'

4.2 The social consequences of the crisis on (dis)trust of young unemployed

4.2.1 The relation with neighbourhood

Broadly speaking participants have no strong links with the neighbourhood. In some cases the neighbours are elderly and none of them referred to do joint activities. Although, one participant stated to have the understanding and encouragement of her neighbours concerning the fact of being unemployed: *'People tell me to be calm, to be patient, 'oh it is very little time has passed since (...) This is now normal, there are many people like that, there are many young people looking for a job.'*

4.2.2 The relation with family

The majority of the testimonies highlighted having strong family's ties. Family is considered as a crucial source of support during hard times. It gives support with financial help, food or share holiday costs when are spent together. When divorce happens the older children leave school and start working to help on the family budget. Nonetheless there are other participants who don't have any family support. Quite the contrary, to whom was denied family help when it was most needed:

'I was nine years old when my mother died. My father asked for help to his family but they only thought in themselves, didn't want help others. And my father didn't have possibilities because he worked from 8 am to midnight. I left home during some time...I had a surgery to a leg and I went to one lady's home and I have been there many years. Then my father died two years ago. I stayed in my father's house with my brother.'

4.2.3 The relation with social organisations and public services

In general the provision of social organisations answers are positively perceived. They have food support and trust in the quality of services and care of people's lives. Some of them are engaged on voluntary work because they believe in the work done in helping vulnerable people. Regarding the public services like social security or public employment service are often viewed negatively. With concerns to public servants of the social security it is pointed out:

'They don't want to know (social security). They know that people go through difficulties but they don't want to listen to their problems. So my advice is to go to entities, for example the Red Cross who cares, who takes time to listen to your story ... That's their mission and do not take anything for it ...'

The same participant pointed out that:

'The lady (Social Security) told my father: "You are not poor." I am not poor but I'm in economic difficulties, it's just me to care of three children. I want to know why you are withdrawing the support now when I need it most. The woman said, "Let me see: you have a house, right? Sell it and you won't need to go abroad." It makes no sense. For the social security employee we had to sell the house as a way to not emigrate.'

4.2.4 Employment public service

From the participants' point of view there is a lack of satisfaction towards job centre professionals in providing information about traineeships and job offers:

'From the traineeships, the lady gave me the sheet that was on the internet and I ended up not realising about what were the employers charges. The lady did not know how to answer my doubts, and about the training told me to go

there Wednesday at 10 that would be an information session. There are people who cannot go there on Wednesday at 10 am.'

Another statement refers: *'I went this morning to know my situation, if everything was right, if there was any labour supply. (...) "Go to the site to see." It is the second time that gives the same answer.'*

Moreover, professional training addressed to unemployed people as an active labour market policy is regarded as a statistics matter: *'The State does not care about people, cares about numbers ...'* A relevant feature is that employer's don't value the training undertaken by the employment public service:

'... My mother attended a cooking course for a year to get the 9th grade. (...) Employers look at it and think: she hadn't learning anything. The employer doesn't value this training education. Doesn't provide a job. It is for the State say to Brussels that we are not unemployed. (...) A person goes there and squeezing it, you don't learn anything.'

Beyond that, people's participation in training is viewed as compulsory attendance with no freedom to choose the content areas more suitable with the working experience or education background: *'we get there and we can't choose between two courses... it is imposed. This should be a democracy. It's not just elections.'*

Moreover, the training offer is targeted only to low skilled people, ignoring the more qualified groups: *'... If you have a lower education level anything goes (...) there was no training for me (...) and I would not receive information ... by the fact of having a degree on the health area ...'*

4.2.5 Trust in politicians and political institutions

Young unemployed people shared their negative opinion towards politicians during the focus groups discussions. They look at politicians behaviours ruled by self-interest instead of being conducted by social welfare values and the common interest to improve people's quality of life. In the context of political youth organisations, one young unemployed participant currently belongs to the Socialist youth Party and participated already in different youth parties. He reached the conclusion that there are few people who are truly interested in solving social problems. They are interested to get a job, public recognition or social status. Another similar experience is shared with student's union and student's election: *'If at the level of an academic association is like this, I don't want to imagine how it will be politics at real stage...'* The idea of political ethics was considered to exist on the early ages of the democratic regime in Portugal after the dictatorship: *'... politicians were taken seriously. (Alvaro Cunhal – communist leader, Sá Carneiro- social democratic leader). People believed in what they did and what they wanted to do. They did it by public interest, now it is much for 'their pocket'.* The political system is viewed as being discredited:

'Nobody believes in politicians. There are few people to believe (...) there are always good politicians and they really want to do things, and they want to show...but the majority of them doesn't think like that.(...) If you ask people, they tell you that they are all equal and are all liars.'

In the context of the political elections (4th October 2015) participants were very critical to the political marketing of government parties' coalition - Social Democratic Party (PSD) and Christians Conservatives (PP-CDS):

'People say yes I want Portugal Ahead, I want to vote in Portugal Ahead. (...) "And what do you think about Passos Coelho ...? Passos Coelho I don't want to hear that name!" It was the same party. People were all voting in Portugal Ahead thinking it was another party ...Neither I did know who the Portugal Ahead was. Afterwards I realised ... Jesus!'

Even regards the attempt to solve the economic and social crisis at European level by the European institutions there isn't a favourable opinion:

'I think the crisis is the banks fault. The European institutions don't care and don't know how to manage the crisis and in the end, everything will end in a civil war. This is a bit exaggerated and I'm 'making' movies but it is my opinion.'

When participants were questioned about **what do you would like to see changed in politics?** The answer was investing in young people and citizens in general:

'Changing the vision they have about young people (...) they should emphasise our skills. Give us support ... and ... create opportunities.' and *'To help more the Portuguese people.'*

The investment should be mainly in health care and education:

'Improve the health care services! Do not cut back on the health.';
'In education as well! Because I think that young people have the potential and capacity to have good results.'

4.2.6 Debate about refugees rights

The recent wave of refugees across Europe was a controversial issue from the social and economic rights perspective in a context of social and economic crisis by who is in a vulnerable situation. Concerning refugees there is an ambivalent position: on one hand it is pointed out that it is offered many conditions to the refugees: *'a family who came to Ovar and got a whole house arranged with furniture and jobs'*, raising the question why offer so much at once if there is homeless people, nobody wants to know if they have home or not. It was added that: *'(...) I think it became an aid boom, a social project to help Portuguese wouldn't be so accepted.'* One the other hand, it is stated that there is:

'... Also people who are silly and tell them to go to other countries ... I don't think so. We should think if we were on their situation ... if Portugal had some problem we also wanted to be well accepted. I think it was a lot of confusion around this.'

Moreover, it was called the media responsibility to this issue, the information conveyed reinforces the prejudice and discrimination among native citizens towards refugees in the sense that:

'The media does not help. It gives the idea that we will give everything but it is not quite so, we will give a lot, yes we will. And people then start saying that we will give everything ...'

4.2.7 The young unemployed perspective about human rights

'I think that it's more important than having someone here to talk about what our rights are ... it would be much better to happen but there will be no changes soon in my opinion... More than that, it would be more useful if someone give us tools to deal with the current society ...'

Human Rights are viewed as an idealistic and abstract concept inscribed in legislation far from being fully implemented. From this point of view one of the social damage of the crisis is the deterioration of human rights, especially the economic and social rights by the difficulties to access work, or to have precarious jobs without social protection, as well as when young unemployed face a long period of time searching for the first job without any benefit. There is an awareness of the right to work as an entitlement that everyone should have, the fact is that there are no jobs in the labour market which constrains people freedoms and choices. In this sense, the right to have a job is being violated which raises the pressure to mobilise strategies to be well succeeded in the labour market:

Today we are so many around the same, that we have to learn strategies to sell our skills on the labour market. Why are you an added value for a company? (...) what is in our hands to do? What techniques, we young people have to overcome the situation. (...) How can we 'sell us' in this labour market?

To know the fundamental rights is viewed as an individual responsibility matter and not as an empowering tool to transform social reality through public discussion and advocacy:

'Now to talk about our rights I think it depends on each of us try to find out. If we don't worry about it we do not worry about anything.'

Finally, some of them answer the question about the meaning of Human Rights having in mind their situation as young unemployed: *'The right to be heard'; 'Freedom of speech and not to be discriminated'; 'The right to work'; 'I don't know...I never thought about that...I don't know.'* To sum up, the human rights need to be deeply debated on how can be a crucial tool in their own lives.

5. Conclusion

The global economic crisis has challenged the quality of the life standards of many people with great emphasis on the most vulnerable people. In the Portuguese context the number of poor people increased and became poorer. High unemployment, low employment, the increase on poverty and social exclusion, and declining household incomes resulted in a lack of confidence in political and economic institutions. This report aims to understand how the crisis and anti-crisis measures undermined the social rights and the disinvestment of the ten young unemployed aged 18-30 years in São João da Madeira (Portugal). The focus on the young people's testimonies aims to gather data on the social damage of the crisis through their own voices far from the purpose of being representative, having in mind the number of young people being heard. Instead, it aims to bring an overview of how people's lives have been affected by the economic crisis and show the living experience beyond statistics. However, it is important to highlight that the anxieties felt to get a job is very representative to young people to whom emigration is not a 'free choice' and reflects the structural increase of the emigration rate in the last years.

The research questions which guide this report and were formulated in chapter 4 are answered here:

Young people continue to face more difficulties in entering and remaining in the labour market, as well as in accessing quality jobs. Their capabilities were deteriorated by being forced to emigrate, to not have freedom of choice of training or the right to a decent job.

All participants or their families received RSI the social benefit that shows the degree to which poverty and social exclusion deprive their rights. Despite the level of education, all participants agreed on having more education increases the changes in the future. As unemployed people they perceived as underqualified or overqualified to integrate the labour market. The participants with low levels of education and qualification, (9th or 12th degree) did not enrol for secondary or college due to economic reasons. Instead proceed to vocation training to raise the opportunities to get a job. Who attended higher education had support from the State or a relative who has to emigrate. To have a degree as the first member of the household was viewed as a family dream and a way to have a better life far from the parents' working class background, this turned into a 'postponed dream' to find a job. Furthermore, the unemployed young people in our study feel the pressure to not stop and continue enriching their curricula as a way to fight for a job. However, their education options are deeply dependent of what the economy dictates. They do not feel free to choose the study area they want but the one the labour market needs. At this concern human rights are not being foreseen. Education is considered merely as an instrumental value to promote productivity and sees the human being as a restrict notion of human capital. According to the capability approach education is relevant in terms of individual well-being and freedom, as well as reinforcing social cohesion, democracy and human rights by reducing poverty and inequality. On the one hand, education is a vehicle for accessing better jobs which potentially create opportunities and enlarge individual freedom 'to do and to be' and realise important dimensions of well-being and of critical and active citizenship, like to be able to communicate and to participate in community's life, and ability to pursue one's life goals. On the other hand, the lack of real opportunities constraints young people to enter in the labour market affecting different well-being domains of their lives like starting by the basic material living conditions and it is a waste of knowledge that could contribute to the economic growth of a country.

Young unemployed are losing confidence in how labour market institutions rule job conditions: offering low wages, few and precarious jobs. Their right to work is constrained by the requirement of previous work experience. They call on the responsibility towards society and the economic actors for not being aware of their potential, knowledge and willingness to work. The participants of the study find it unfair that work experience of 3 or 4 years is required without having a chance to prove their value. Search for a job is perceived as very frustrating because never have a reply from a direct contact with companies or when sending CVs.

There is an ambiguous feeling about how to overcome unemployment. On one hand the participants in our research view unemployment as a structural issue and do not believe in an economic recovery in the near future. It is not considered an individual matter to which they can be blamed for. On the other hand they are aware of the need to be flexible and to accept bad work conditions as a starting point. Some of the participants with a degree try to accept blue colour jobs and not give up of trying, to earn some money and fight for the work they want in another big city, or get more training. But even for unskilled jobs it is required to have experience. When there is an opportunity to start to work according to their qualifications, jobs are paid as unskilled jobs. Concerning to low qualified young unemployed had a precarious work experience. Broadly speaking emigration is a way to get a job mainly in the nursing area where there is a huge demand from companies with a guarantee of being employed. Nonetheless it is not a free option. Young people rather prefer to stay, but they feel forced to go abroad to have a job. For an unemployed male, the undeclared work is no longer an option due to the crisis, such as in the construction or in the restaurant sector. There is a common feeling of loss of dignity of the working conditions. It became much worse during the economic crisis with the increasing work hours without payment. The participants felt they are losing trust in the labour market and in people.

With regards social protection, all participants have some kind of social support due to their vulnerable context: family allowance; social minimum income; unemployed benefits; scholarships, social house; social canteens. The amount of the benefits was reduced during the economic crisis. The Social Insertion Income decreased and the rules have been even harder to access. The conditionality of the social income benefits produce the risk of restrained incentives to take up part-time work for instance.

In participants' words social investments are replaced for neo liberal policies. The priority in bank rescue and the cuts in social benefits provoke distrust in participants.

The scope of the relatives' diseases are very linked with the unemployed effects, as a multi-dimensional phenomenon that affects several dimensions of the human well-being (even it is not a linear relation between causes and consequences) like depression, domestic violence and divorce as well as health problems spread among family members. In these cases, the health expenses are a burden to the family budget, and the money available is driven to the priority cases. Despite the fact that there were made remarkable improvements in health over last decades, the increase of the emergency fees makes harder the access of the most vulnerable people to health care and worsened the working conditions of health professionals. It was stated that there had been cuts in health under the effectiveness discourse and attempt to maintain the same services, with a reduction of the health professionals.

Relating to housing participants shared some housing problems mainly dampness, missing heating conditions in winter and difficulties to pay the rent. Almost half of the participant group can pay the rent with their household's income and another half have social support to do it. In some cases, even having social support it is difficult to manage to pay the bills. The majority of the participants do not have money to afford a week's vacation over the past decade with all the expenses paid.

With regards to the negative social consequences leads to a growing distrust and loss of solidarity of young people are concerned, firstly they have no strong links with the neighbourhood broadly speaking. Who do have it, reports a common concern with being unemployed and supports with

courage to overcome this stage in life? The family support is the one that makes the difference to cope with adversity, emotional and financial help, supplies food or share holiday costs when are spent together. When there is not a strong family support, friends are stated as the most important help she/he can have. In the same line of thought it is considered the support given by social organisations. Young unemployed trust in the quality of services and care of people's lives. Some of them are engaged on voluntary work because they believe in the work done in helping vulnerable people. A different opinion regarding the public services is shared, like social security and the public employment service which are often viewed negatively. The participants considered public servants of social security as not being interested in the personal lives or committed to solve social problems by the way clarifications are provided. The social organisations are viewed as the ones who try to solve problems to whom are in need.

With regards to employment public servants, usually they share the opinion they do not give them the information they need, instead they tell them to visit the website to search for a job or to come in another time to have a special answer when will be developed awareness and information session. When this happens they felt not being respected as unemployed. They might have also other things or commitments. Regarding the active labour market policies, the training courses are not valued by companies it is seen as a government strategy to hide high unemployed rates. Training has a compulsory attendance and in participant's words is not allowed to choose the training course which fits best to their education or professional area. This is viewed as a matter of democracy and having the free will to choose and negotiate what suites best to their professional interests. In this sense they advocate that employment public services should invest in an individualised approach to provide more efficient answers.

The participants distrust politicians and political institutions. There is the common idea that politicians run public affairs by self-interest and to win elections, putting aside the people's life conditions. This idea is interiorised even when young people participate or participated in political youth parties and students unions. They claim that politicians must invest in people's lives like education and health.

The participants in our research mostly do not have money to pay for leisure time, holidays and basic needs. Their daily routines encompass struggling with economic worries.

In the current economic crisis the refugees came to light by expressing the few social rights to vulnerable people who already live in the country. At the same time it was drawing attention to the responsible role of media to inform people about this matter and considered as issue of human rights.

The meaning of Human Rights for young unemployed is in first hand: 'the right to work'; 'the right to be heard'; 'freedom of speech and not to be discriminated'. By facing the difficulties to get a job, some of them considered themselves as a resource to companies and therefore have to mobilise different skills and be constantly updated by training to face a competitive market. Therefore, human rights are taken as abstract nature and in near future will not be achieved in the context of economic crisis.

Finally, the negative impacts of the economic crisis in human rights, individual and collective capabilities challenge concrete policies of social investment should be addressed. This brings the need to strongly debate through a public discussion an alternative to the current liberal economic system. What extend this does not imply to think about other social contract by rethinking ethically the notion of human being in terms of effective human rights; by rethinking the role welfare state and the role of the effective social responsibility of companies; by rethinking the sustainable development of generation's well-being. Social investment change society for better and active inclusion and EU must truly put people in the heart of social policy.

To sum up, the young people who participated in our research ask from political actors and institutions a real investment in people to improve their lives in education and health in order to have hope in their future. Moreover, politicians, labour market and civil society should regard

young people as an investment and promote their inclusion in having access to jobs. They could participate in society and help to improve national economy as free people without being enforced to go abroad. The current research findings of the social damages of the crises on young unemployed will be developed further in the next stages of the RE-InVEST project. The special focus for Portugal will be on Active Labour Market Policies as well as Social Protection policies.

appendix 1 Participant Profile

Name	Age	Household	Education level	Period of unemployment	Employment situation	Social support	Informal labour
A	24	Father, mother and sister	Master on ecology and degree on biology [Mother – 9 th level; Father – 12 th level RVCC; sister finishing degree]	From September 2015	Search for first employment [Mother: Invalid/ unemployed six years ago. Worked: in an office; as a maid to take care of children and the house Father: Unemployed; Worked in electricity, distribution of those VHS tapes, factory footwear]	Parents have no income from work. Social benefits: disability allowance and social minimum income; total amount is less than the minimum wage. Food support average of 4 times per year Family support in hardest times	Mother: do cleaning one afternoon at the home of a relative. Father: doing odd jobs for people they know /electricity
B	24	Mother and sister (divorced parents)	Master and degree on psychology Mother: 12th level, Accounting, Professional Training; Sister: Finishing 12 ^o	From November 2015	Search for first employment Mother: manager of a small company of shoes. worked in insurance, accounting; but always was privy footwear	Mother: Salary slightly above minimum wage. Sister: Part-time work at week-ends in bar. Started working two months Receive food by a social organisation	Not applicable
C	18	Mother, one sister two brothers (single parent family)	secondary education/ training education on events organisation	From May 2015	Search for first employment. Volunteer in Associação Ecos Urbanos; Mother unemployed for a long time; Worked in footwear, hairdresser, in sales and the last work footwear, cleanings	Social Income by social security and receive food and other kind of support by a social organisation; the pension of my father's food and family allowance.	Not applicable
D	32	Son(2 years) and wife	9 years of education	From November 2013	Unemployed Work in different jobs (shoes and car factories; restaurants, vigilant guard and was unemployed between jobs Wife: unemployed; worked in restaurants	S289 €/Social minimum income (RSI) 35€/family allowance; social housing benefits	In restaurants, not recently
E	23	One brother and one sister, father is abroad Angola; mother abandoned family	Nursing degree; Brother: didn't finish college. He stopped is studies and began as vigilant in part-time, and put his studies aside and stood in the company. Sister: attending college	From June 2015	Search for first employment	Bother: Work in shifts/ higher than the minimum wage.	Not applicable

Name	Age	Household	Education level	Period of unemployment	Employment situation	Social support	Informal labour
F	22	Mother and sister(single parent family)	Secondary education/training education on beauty treatments and massage	From April 2015	Search for 1st employment		Works during weekends and sometimes days of the week in a hairdresser
G	20	Father, mother, sister, brother	Secondary education/training education on laboratory analysis; Father: 12 th level; Mother: 4 th level	From June 2015 Father: unemployed year ago	Search for 1st employment Father: retired for disability; worked on the boats during 5 years, the contract ended and was maintenance technician in a shopping Mother: employed at a shoe factory. Before worked on restaurant.	Food assistance per month (Habitat); per year (Ecos); Social Housing benefits (due to father disease) and Family allowance of the two brothers	Not applicable
H	23	Brother (father and mother dead)	9 Years of education/training education on bakery; Brother: 6 th level	From November 2014	Unemployed; Worked in a bakery during 7 years Brother: Employed (4 years) in Shoes industry; Father worked in a car factory	Minimum wage/ Food assistance/ social canteens lunch and dinner all days of the week	Few hours last week. (shoe factory)Exception
I**	26	Daughters and the father of her Daughters	9 Years of education/training education logistics	From 2009	Temporary jobs and training courses	Minimum Wage	Not applicable
J	24	Boyfriend and his sons	Secondary education/training education on events organisation and hairdresser. Attended professional courses: first aid in geriatrics; First aid Hydrotherapy; child health care; traditional Portuguese cuisine; and HCCP; Boyfriend: 9 th level	From April 2015 Longest job duration: 9 months vs shortest job duration: week to week	Temporary jobs in restaurant, café, textile factories; quality control; grape harvest; train company. Boyfriend: started work in December 2015; Was unemployed last year (full year); worked in restaurant.	Received unemployed benefits until 16 th Nov. it will ask for RSI Without social support; received unemployment allowance November 2015. Can ask for RSI in march (to receive it ask the three months of bank account or come some money there in the least, transfers ... as I received unemployment benefits have no right ...); Food assistance by social canteens (without choice) Resorted to banks, friends, acquaintances and family. All refused.	Not applicable
L***	20	Father, mother and sister	11 years of education	From March 2015	Temporary jobs in restaurant (6 months part-time) factory		Not applicable

Identification of the group: 10 participants (2 male, 8 female)

** I member gave up of participating

***Participant L got a job in a supermarket and on 4th December 2015 left the group

appendix 2 Drawing methodology

Visual methods (Drawings) reflecting the impact of unemployment (feelings, attitudes and consequences) in young people voices²⁶:

A | Delivering the curriculum on employer's hands. The meaning was a feeling of frustration in searching for a job.

B | A clock and a person with many doubts and questions

C | Three professional stages to get a job

²⁶ The young unemployed testimonies are here presented in summarized way. The long texts are transcribed and analysed.

D| on the different places where I worked in, I felt that after 2008 it has been more **distrust and the alarmism** undermined interpersonal relations, between colleagues due the insecurity felt by the possibility to become unemployed. Even when the job is not the most desirable it is better to have a job than being unemployed. *Observation:* HC didn't deliver his drawing

E| I have a degree (nursing) and this now is my life: I could go on the easiest way but at the same time is very difficult. What I'm talking about is to emigrate...

F| My drawing means confusion....

G| The drawing talks about me. What I want is working, have a driver's license and money.

I| The meaning of drawing is to have a better future (...) to have a salary to help my family.

J| I look at me and I see my situation. And this means which future my children will have? If now is like this, how will it be in a couple of years?

L| My drawing is all the problems that I have: without support from Town Council, from employment services.... Health problems without money ... I am exempted from paying health taxes but I have to do exams and I will have to pay. My boyfriend is ill on an arm and has to do an exam which costs 80€ but I don't have money to pay and I don't have any help.

M| I became unemployed and instead of staying at home I thought in ways of making a better world. So I signed up in a political party (socialist) and became a volunteer in the Red Cross to feel better but I'm still revolted with crisis. I think the crisis is the banks fault. The European institutions don't care and don't know how to manage the crisis and in the end, everything will end in a civil war. This is a bit exaggerated and I'm 'making' movies but it is my opinion.

appendix 3 Snake timetable: presentation of the most relevant austerity measures in Portugal from 2008 to 2015

2008 nationalisation of BPN

- 7.6% Unemployment rate
- 10% Youth NEET - 'Not in Education, Employment, or Training'. (15 -24 ages)
- 15% Youth NEET - 'Not in Education, Employment, or Training'. (25 -29 ages)
- 10.4% Youth work part-time
- 17.9% Risk of poverty
- 20,357 Permanent emigrants

2010 Privatisation of ANA (Portuguese Airports)

- 21% VAT rate
- 23% Tax rate
- 1% Increase of IRS 2nd and 3rd levels
- Cut in jobless benefits

2011 MAY - TROIKA in Portugal

- Sale of EDP to Chinese company
- 15% Rising prices in transport
- 5% to 23% Increase in VAT
- Increase in the price of natural gas and electricity
- The civil service wage was frozen
- Cut on pensions above 1500 euros
- Cuts in the health sector and public companies
- Cut the holiday and Christmas subsidies to civil servants and to all senior pensioners with pensions more than a thousand euros
- TROIKA requires cuts on holiday and Christmas bonuses in the private sector
- Increase user fees: 5 € in health centres and 20 € in the emergency room

2012 Public debt reached 126.6% of GDP

- Investment Reduction in Health
- 14,000 Students in the School Feeding Programme Strengthening
- 20, 8% Dropout rate
- 20.1% Youth working part-time
- New rules for mobility for public employees will suffer a significant cut in their remuneration
- 10% cut of unemployment benefits after six months and 540 days maximum grant
- The Christmas bonuses and vacation in the civil service will only be replaced in 2015
- 14.9% Unemployment rate
- 25 to 26.5% of capital taxation income from capital and capital gains

2013

- 500,000 Jobs destroyed since 2008-2013
- 19.5% of people at risk of poverty
- 3.5% of its population emigrated between 2011 and 2013
- 31.6% Child poverty rate
- 19.5% Risk of poverty
- 17.7% Unemployment rate
- Increase from 35 to 40 hours per week in the Civil Service
- Increase the retirement age to 66 years
- Youth Average Age of leaving the parental home (M = 30 and F = 29 years)
- 15% Youth NEET - not in education, not working (15 -24 ages)
- 20% Youth NEET - not in education, not working (25 -29 ages)

JUNE 2014 | ADJUSTMENT PROGRAM END OF ECONOMIC | TROIKA

- VAT rises to 23.25%
- Single Social Tax of workers rises to 11.2%
- Minimum wage rises to 505 euros
- 35% Youth unemployment rate
- 49,572 Permanent emigrants

2015

- 12% Unemployment rate
- 60% of the unemployed are long-lasting no more than 12 months and 46% for more than 24 months
- 19% of workers with temporary work contracts
- Portugal 9th most unequal country in the OECD/May
- 592,000 beneficiaries lose access to social benefits for children between October 2010 and August

Adjustment program: reduction of expenditure involved:

- Cut of EUR 500 million per year in health
- Cut pensions above € 1,500
- Cuts in education 175 million per year

appendix 4 Snake timetable: the most relevant events of all group from 2008 to 2015 | Group exercise

appendix 5 Snake timetable: the most relevant individual episodes from 2008 to 2015 | Individual exercise

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RE-InVEST - Rebuilding an Inclusive, Value-based Europe of Solidarity and Trust through Social Investments

In 2013, as a response to rising inequalities, poverty and distrust in the EU, the Commission launched a major endeavour to rebalance economic and social policies with the Social Investment Package (SIP). RE-InVEST aims to strengthen the philosophical, institutional and empirical underpinnings of the SIP, based on social investment in human rights and capabilities. Our consortium is embedded in the 'Alliances to Fight Poverty'. We will actively involve European citizens severely affected by the crisis in the co-construction of a more powerful and effective social investment agenda with policy recommendations.

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